

NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION INTO THE EFFECT OF NON-UNIFORM INLET PRESSURE PROFILES ON THE HOT GAS INGESTION OF THE STATOR-ROTOR CAVITY

Zhe Jia

Shaanxi Engineering
Laboratory of
Turbomachinery and Power
Equipment, Institute of
Turbomachinery, School of
Energy and Power
Engineering, Xi'an Jiaotong
University, Xi'an, China

Zhao Liu

Shaanxi Engineering
Laboratory of
Turbomachinery and Power
Equipment, Institute of
Turbomachinery, School of
Energy and Power
Engineering, Xi'an Jiaotong
University, Xi'an, China

Zhenping Feng

Shaanxi Engineering
Laboratory of
Turbomachinery and Power
Equipment, Institute of
Turbomachinery, School of
Energy and Power
Engineering, Xi'an Jiaotong
University, Xi'an, China

Abstract

In modern gas turbine, the hot gas ingestion severely threatens the safety during operation and service life due to the increase of the turbine inlet temperature. The hot gas ingestion is closely related to the mainstream condition. Therefore, the investigation of the ingestion under nonuniform inlet pressure profile of the mainstream is in need for further understandings. A comprehensive computation was performed in this paper to study the effect of the nonuniform inlet pressure profile on the ingestion with four profiles, two rim seal configurations and four sealing flowrates for each configuration. The results showed that the high total pressure near the hub induces greater peak to trough pressure difference at the vane exit, which is enlarged about 10% compared to the uniform inlet. This increase leads to more ingestion. An analysis of the velocity field of V_{cir} and V_{rad} found that the radial velocity gradient increases the nonuniformity of V_{cir} and V_{rad} , leading to more complex flow structure inside of the rim seal. An obvious area of negative V_{rad} is found for the radial rim seal at $\Phi=0.04$ when imposing the profile with high pressure near the hub, meaning that the ingestion might be more severe under the real condition.

Keywords: Hot gas ingestion, Non-uniform inlet, Turbine rim seal, Unsteady flow.

Nomenclature

b	radius of seal
c	concentration of tracer gas
$c_{CO_2,air}$	concentration of CO_2 at outlet
$c_{CO_2,in}$	concentration of CO_2 at inlet
$c_{CO_2,local}$	local concentration of CO_2

C_{ax}	axial chord length
C_p	pressure difference ()
C_{p-a}	pressure difference with $\Phi=0.001$
$C_{p-a,max}$	maximum of C_{p-a}
$C_{p-a,min}$	minimum of C_{p-a}
$C_{p,in}$	pressure difference at inlet
f	frequency
g	width of cavity
H	height of vane and blade
\dot{m}	mass flow rate
P_s	local static pressure
$P_{s,ave}$	circumferential averaged static pressure
$P_{s,max}$	maximum static pressure
$P_{s,min}$	minimum static pressure
$P_{t,in}$	local total pressure at inlet
$P_{t,in,mid}$	total pressure at the midspan of inlet
s_{ax}	axial rim seal width
s_c	seal clearance
s_{rd}	axial rim seal height
V_{cir}	velocity in the circumferential direction
$V_{cir,real}$	calculated tangential velocity
ΔC_p	nondimensional pressure difference

Greek

ε	sealing effectiveness
ρ	density
θ	nondimensional angle
Ω	rotating speed
Φ	nondimensional sealing flow parameter
τ	timestep

1. INTRODUCTION

The hot gas ingestion is a crucial problem in modern gas turbine research, which means that the high temperature mainstream enters the space between the stator and rotor disks. The hot gas causes thermal erosion and fatigue of the disks and eventually impacts the operating safety of gas turbines. To prevent the ingestion, rim seal structures and secondary compressed air are employed to seal this space and protect the stator and rotor disks. As Scobie et al. [1] reported, the hot gas ingestion is affected importantly by the mainstream conditions. Thus, it is essential for the ingestion mechanism to figure out the effect of non-uniform inlet.

Previous studies have mainly focused on the impact of non-uniform inflow on the aerothermal and cooling characteristics of nozzle guide vanes (NGV). Barringer et al. [2,3] carried out a series of experiments to make a summary of typical inlet profiles of combustor swirler, including the pressure's and temperature's, and figure out how the profile influences the endwall heat transfer and vane flow field of HP turbine. Wang et al. [4] applied the inlet profiles, extracted from Ref. [2,3], and hot streaks to the numerical investigation of GE-E3 stage to find out the effect of these variants on the aerothermal performance. Simonassi et al. [5] used steady and unsteady measurements to study the effect of different inlet total pressure distortions and clocking positions on the aerodynamic and aeroelastic performance. Wang et al. [6] numerically assessed the effect of the nonuniform inlet boundaries on the NGV's film cooling behavior. It found that the positive swirl may improve the film cooling effectiveness. Li et al. [7] quantified the effect of the nonuniform inlet boundary uncertainty on the NGV's aerothermal characteristics.

Researchers carried out a lot of experiments and models to interpret the interaction between the sealing egress of the disk cavity and the main flow in the annulus space. Patinios et al. [8] developed the measurements of a 1.5 stage turbine for the ingestion research and the modeling of the ingestion assessment. Scobie et al. [9,10] studied the effect of the sealing flow egress on the interaction with the main flow and the sealing improvement of the downstream disk cavity. It was confirmed that the asymmetric variation of the sealing effectiveness through the rim seal and the outer part of the disk cavity. Dawson et al. [11] demonstrated that the hot gas ingestion depends on the amplitude and frequency of the pressure fluctuation in the rim seal. Graikos et al. [12] introduced the swirl ratio as a new parameter to the low order model to predict the hot gas ingestion. Savov and Atkins [13] established a prediction model about the sealing effectiveness of stator-rotor cavity relating to the secondary flowrate based on turbulent transport. Monge-Concepción et al. [14] found that the coolant from vane trailing edge reduces the pressure unsteadiness in the rim seal by an experiment under engine-like conditions. Mesny et al. [15] investigated the vortex interactions between the sealing egress and main stream with a non-axisymmetric rotor hub using PIV method. It was captured that the combination of the horse vortex and the egress vortex. Barsi et al. [16] pointed out that the interaction of the sealing egress and main flow introduces the

efficiency loss of turbine rows by using an experimental-validated computation.

Apart from the works above, the numerical method was widely developed to investigate the hot gas ingestion in the turbine disk cavity. Gao et al. [17], [18] compared the results of LES, URANS and RANS about the sealing flow in stator-rotor cavity with a chute seal. All turbulent models show reasonable agreement with the experiment data, while only the LES model could predict the pressure spectrum accurately. De Cosmo et al. [19] computed the floe structures in the rim seal under different sector sizes, sealing flow rates and off-design condition and indicated that the results show no difference of the sector sizes. Xue et al. [20] found the inhomogeneity of the ingestion in axial and circumferential direction and modified the Orifice model [1]. Xie et al. [21] constructed a new model based on penetration depth to assess the hot gas ingestion by using a validated DES turbulent model. Burden et al. [22] compared the computational flow field of some reported rim seal structures by using multiple turbulent models and different boundary layer treatments and pointed out the URANS SST and LES show similarity in prediction, which is also consistent with the experiment. Cong et al. [23] imposed swirl angles on the inlet mainstream and computed its effect on rim sealing. It reported that the positive swirl angle improves the sealing performance.

As the previous papers present, many measurement techniques and computation method were developed to research the non-uniform inlet pressure profiles and the hot gas ingestion. It is still in lack of the research for associating the hot gas ingestion with the non-uniform inlet pressure profiles. Therefore, the effect of non-uniform inlet profile on the hot gas ingestion was numerically investigated based on the Bath stage model. A comprehensive computation was carried out by four types of inlet total pressure profiles, two rim seal configurations and four secondary flowrates for each configuration. The effect of the non-uniform inlet was analyzed first by the result of the radial rim seal. And the flow field near the seal was compared for four secondary flow rates and the axial rim seal.

2. COMPUTATIONAL DOMAIN AND METHODOLOGY VALIDATION

In the study presented, the computational domain is derived from the Bath stage model [9]. The first stage is retained and the second row of vane is removed for focusing the ingestion in the upstream disk cavity. The main flow path is extended 1.5 times of C_{ax} upstream to the vanes and 1.0 times of C_{ax} downstream to the blades to avoid the boundary effect. **Fig. 1** shows the 3D computational domain and its geometric parameters. In **Fig. 1a**, the stator part in red is stationary, which contains two vane passages. The rotor and disk cavity in blue is rotating with a speed of 3000rpm. The rotor contains three blade passage. All three parts form the whole computational domain, occupying 22.5 degree in circumferential direction. In **Fig. 1b**, the geometric parameters of the computational domain are defined. The characteristic length of this domain is defined as the radius of the rim seal inner side, which is 0.19m and represented by b . H is the passage height of vane and blade. The axial rim seal

width (in solid) and the radial rim seal height (in dashed) are s_{ax} and s_{rd} , respectively. The width of the disk cavity is symbolled by g . Detailed information of the geometric parameters are in Ref. [9].

FIGURE 1: THE COMPUTATIONAL DOMAIN AND BOUNDARY NAMES.

In order to obtain convincing results, the numerical method was meticulously validated by mesh independence test, turbulent model validation and time step validation. The GCI method was used to examine the mesh independence test. Three sizes of structured mesh (Coarse, Medium, Fine) were constructed by ANSYS ICEM, corresponding to the mesh number of 1.6, 3.2 and 6.4 million. Their results were compared by the parameter ΔC_p , which is the nondimensional peak-to-trough pressure difference at the exit of the vanes. The definitions of C_p and ΔC_p are shown in Eq.1 and Eq.2:

$$C_p = \frac{P_s}{0.5 * \rho \Omega^2 b^2} \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta C_p = \frac{P_{s,max} - P_{s,min}}{0.5 * \rho \Omega^2 b^2} \quad (2)$$

in Eq.1, the P_s represents the local static pressure. ρ is the reference density, Ω is the rotating speed. In Eq.2, the $P_{s,max}$ and $P_{s,min}$ are the maximum pressure and the minimum pressure at the vane exit, respectively.

Table 1 presents the computed ΔC_p and GCI index. The relative variation to the extrapolated ΔC_p comes to 0.06% when using the fine mesh, considered as a mesh independent result. Therefore, the fine mesh is applied for this study. The first layer of mesh was 0.001mm to promise an appropriate y^+ lower than 1.

Table 1: MESH INDEPENDENCE TEST

Name	Mesh number ($\times 10^6$)	ΔC_p	Relative variation (%)
Coarse	1.6	0.276811	1.32
Medium	3.2	0.273895	0.29
Fine	6.4	0.273334	0.06
Extrapolated	-	0.273200	

According to the references about the hot gas ingestion, the unsteady SST model was adopted for simulation due to its good agreement with experiment result and cost of computation resource. **Fig. 2** presents the sealing effectiveness (ε) predicted by the SST model during the nondimensional sealing flow parameter (Φ) variation. The ε is defined in Eq. 3 and the Φ is defined in Eq. 4:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{c_{CO_2,local} - c_{CO_2,air}}{c_{CO_2,in} - c_{CO_2,air}} \quad (3)$$

$$\Phi = \frac{\dot{m}}{\rho * 2\pi b s_c * \Omega b} \quad (4)$$

the ε is defined by the concentration ratio.

The predicted ε is very similar to the experiment data [9].

FIGURE 2: THE SEALING EFFECTIVENESS COMPARISON OF EXPERIMENT AND COMPUTAION

Besides, the time step validation was conducted for finding time-resolved computations. In this validation, four sizes of time step were employed and they are $13.0 \times 10^{-5}s$, $6.3 \times 10^{-5}s$, $4.2 \times 10^{-5}s$, $3.1 \times 10^{-5}s$, represented by τ_0 , τ_1 , τ_2 and τ_3 . The pressure fluctuation of different time steps was monitored and their spectrum distribution were analyzed by FFT in **Fig. 3**. The frequency was nondimensionalized by the basic frequency of 50Hz, corresponding to the rotating speed. The spectrum of τ_2 is similar to that of τ_3 . Thus, the time step of τ_2 , about 0.8 deg per step, was used to get the time-resolved results in the present work.

FIGURE 3: THE FFT OF PRESSURE SIGNALS OF DIFFERENT TIME STEPS

The inlet total pressure profiles were derived from Wang et al. [4]. For the different definition of C_p , it should be pointed out that the inlet total pressure profiles were recalculated and plotted in Fig. 4, of which the vertical axis is the spanwise direction, and the horizontal is the $C_{p,in}$. Its definition is Eq. 5:

$$C_{p,in} = \frac{P_{t,in} - P_{t,in,mid}}{0.5 * \rho \Omega^2 b^2} \quad (5)$$

in Eq. 5, the $P_{t,in}$ is the local total pressure at the inlet, and the $P_{t,in,mid}$ is the total pressure at the midspan of the inlet.

As a reference case, the Profile1 has a uniform inlet total pressure. The total pressure of the Profile2 is close to the Profile1 at the midspan, and lower than the Profile1 near the shroud and hub. The Profile3 is originally derived from Barringer et al. [2,3] as a typical exit profile of combustor swirler. The Profile4 is the radially reversed total pressure of the Profile3.

FIGURE 4: INLET TOTAL PRESSURE PROFILES

The boundary conditions are listed in Table 2. The inlet boundary is imposed by the inlet total pressure profiles and the temperature is set as 320K. The outlet pressure is 101.325kPa. The walls in the fluid domain are considered as adiabatic and no-slip wall. The rotating speed is 3000rpm for the simulation. The ideal air is applied as the main flow and a mixture gas with 97% ideal air and 3% CO2 is applied as the sealing flow. The sealing effectiveness is calculated by the local concentration of CO2.

To figure out the effect of the inlet total pressure profile, a comprehensive computation was conducted, containing 32 cases. For the different sealing flowrate of the rim seal configurations, the sealing flow parameters of the axial rim were set as $\Phi=0.001, 0.02, 0.05$ and 0.1 , while that of the radial rim

were set as $\Phi=0.001, 0.01, 0.02$, and 0.04 . The cases with $\Phi=0.001$ were considered as the no-sealing cases. Four profiles were also imposed on the inlet of every rim configuration and sealing flow parameter. The ANSYS CFX was used to solve the URANS SST turbulent model and the initial field of the transient case was set by its steady solution.

TABLE 2: BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

Parameter	Value
Inlet temperature(K)	320
Outlet pressure(kPa)	101.325
Nondimensional sealing flow parameter(Φ)	0.001, 0.01, 0.02, 0.04, 0.05, 0.1
Rotating Speed(rpm)	3000

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

First, the effect of the inlet total pressure profile is analyzed by the comparisons of the ε , pressure and velocity distributions. And then, the differences of the Φ under various profiles were clarified to figure out details of the hot gas ingestion as the Φ grows. Finally, the rim seal configurations are examined to find the geometric effect on the ingestion with total pressure profiles.

3.1 Effect on the vane exit pressure

Fig. 5 shows the data position. The vane exit pressure is extracted from 1.5mm and 2.5mm downstream of the vane trailing edge. The cutting plane is located at the middle of axial rim seal.

FIGURE 5: DATA POSITION IN THE COMPUTATIONAL DOMAIN

The vane exit pressure of the axial rim at $\Phi=0.001$ is nondimensionalized into C_{p-a} and plotted with a horizontal axis of θ , the nondimensional angle, in Fig. 6. These cases are chosen for the same inlet boundary set for the radial rim cases, resulting in the same exit pressure. And the effect of the sealing flow is avoided as much as possible for the case with $\Phi=0.001$. The C_{p-a} is defined as follows:

$$C_{p-a} = \frac{P_s - P_{s,ave}}{0.5 * \rho \Omega^2 b^2} \quad (6)$$

in which, the $P_{s,ave}$ is the circumferential averaged static pressure. This definition is similar to the C_p 's. The difference is

that the circumferentially averaged pressure is subtracted from the local pressure in the numerator.

a. THE VANE EXIT PRESSURE DISTRIBUTION AT 1.5MM DOWNSTREAM TO THE TRAILING EDGE

b. THE VANE EXIT PRESSURE DISTRIBUTION AT 2.5MM DOWNSTREAM TO THE TRAILING EDGE

FIGURE 6: THE CIRCUMFERENTIAL DISTRIBUTION OF THE VANE EXIT PRESSURE

From Fig. 6a, it is found that the peak pressure is the highest and the trough pressure is the lowest for the Profile3, causing the largest ΔC_p . The main reason for the largest ΔC_p is that the $C_{p,in}$ of the Profile3 is larger than others near the hub. The ΔC_p of the Profile2 is the lowest because both the averaged and hub $C_{p,in}$ of this profile is lower than others, indicating a lower main flowrate and velocity in the annulus space. However, the distributions in Fig. 6b shows that the C_{p-a} of all profiles are very close, even the ΔC_p of the Profile3 seems to be the smallest. Another point noticed is that the distribution of the Profile3 shifts to the left a bit to other distribution in Fig. 6a and 6b.

Table 3 and 4 listed the values about the peak ($C_{p-a,max}$) and trough ($C_{p-a,min}$) pressure, the ΔC_p of the cases in Fig. 6a and 6b. As Table 3 shows, the $C_{p-a,max}$ of the Profile3 is 6.57% larger than that of the Profile1 and the $C_{p-a,min}$ of the Profile3 is 15.03% lower. Consequently, the ΔC_p of the Profile3 increases 9.15% compared to the ΔC_p of the Profile1. As a reversed distribution of the Profile3, the ΔC_p of the Profile4 is only 1.6% larger than that of the Profile1. The variation of C_{p-a} and ΔC_p indicates that the increase of the ΔC_p of the Profile3 is not only due to the increase in main flowrate caused by the rise in total pressure, but also the influence of the high total pressure distribution near the wall. However, the ΔC_p of the Profile3 decreases rapidly, which is almost 4.38% smaller than that of the Profile1. A possible reason for this reduction is that the high velocity near the hub

induces greater dissipation of the nonuniformity of the exit pressure.

TABLE 3: THE VANE EXIT PRESSURE AT 1.5MM DOWNSTREAM TO THE TRAILING EDGE

	Profile1	Profile2	Profile3	Profile4
$C_{p-a,max}$	0.304	0.275	0.324	0.313
$C_{p-a,min}$	-0.133	-0.142	-0.153	-0.131
ΔC_p	0.437	0.417	0.477	0.444

TABLE 4: THE VANE EXIT PRESSURE AT 2.5MM DOWNSTREAM TO THE TRAILING EDGE

	Profile1	Profile2	Profile3	Profile4
$C_{p-a,max}$	0.183	0.185	0.180	0.187
$C_{p-a,min}$	-0.091	-0.082	-0.082	-0.095
ΔC_p	0.274	0.267	0.262	0.282

3.2 Effect on velocity

In addition, the velocity field of the results is analyzed to figure out the effect of the profiles. The contours are extracted from the cutting plane as Fig.5 shows.

Firstly, the velocity in the circumferential direction (V_{cir}) of the axial rim is exhibited in Fig. 7. The results with the same Φ are arranged in the same main row, containing two sub rows. The results of the profiles are placed Profile1, Profile2, Profile3 and Profile4 from the left to the right and from the top to bottom.

The definition of V_{cir} is as follows:

$$V_{cir} = \frac{V_{cir,real}}{\Omega b} \quad (7)$$

in which, the $V_{cir,real}$ is the calculated tangential velocity and Ωb is the line speed at the characteristic radius.

FIGURE 7: THE CIRCUMFERENTIAL VELOCITY DISTRIBUTION AT THE CUTTING PLANE FOR THE AXIAL RIM SEAL

From the figures of $\Phi=0.001$, it can be found that there is a high line of V_{cir} near the rim due to the rotation of the rotor. Three high value regions of V_{cir} are shown in the annulus space in every figure, which are caused by the blade rotation. In addition, the V_{cir} distribution of the Profile3 is obviously larger than others near the rim, which induces larger V_{cir} difference between the main flow and sealing flow. Along with the Φ increase, the V_{cir} is decreased due to low momentum the sealing flow has mixing with the main stream. The contours show difference at $\Phi=0.1$ as well. The V_{cir} of the Profile1 and 4 seem to be more uniform, but the V_{cir} of the Profile2 and 3 shows more nonuniformity. The reason for that might be that both profiles, 2 and 3, have greater radial gradient of the velocity, which inducing more unsteadiness.

FIGURE 8: THE CIRCUMFERENTIAL VELOCITY DISTRIBUTION AT THE CUTTING PLANE FOR THE RADIAL RIM SEAL

Fig. 8 shows the circumferential velocity distributions of the radial rim. The contours of V_{cir} in the annulus show the similar distribution to that of the axial rim, three high regions induced by the blade rotation and a high line near the rim induced by the disk. Comparing the figures of $\Phi=0.02$, the figures of the radial rim shows lower V_{cir} inside of the rim. This is due to more hot gas is blocked by the radial rim from entering the rim. In other word, the ingestion of the radial rim is much lower than that of the axial. At $\Phi=0.04$, the V_{cir} of the Profile3 inside of the rim is larger than others. The reason for that is greater ingestion is induced by the high total pressure near the hub. Therefore, not only the asymmetry of pressure in circumferential but also in radial should be noticed when investigating the hot gas ingestion.

FIGURE 9: THE RADIAL VELOCITY DISTRIBUTION AT THE CUTTING PLANE FOR THE AXIAL RIM SEAL

Fig. 9 presents the radial velocity distribution (V_{rad}) of the axial rim. The definition of V_{rad} is in Eq. 8:

$$V_{rad} = \frac{V_{rad,real}}{\Omega b} \quad (8)$$

in which, the $V_{rad,real}$ is the realistic radial velocity. The positive direction points out of the rim.

At $\Phi=0.001$, there are three pairs of the positive and negative V_{rad} in the contours of the Profile1 and 4, but only one pair can be observed in the Profile2 and 3. The possible reason for this phenomenon is that both the profiles have a greater velocity gradient near the hub, which is mentioned in discussing **Fig. 7**. As the Φ increases, the area of the negative V_{rad} shrinks gradually and disappears at $\Phi=0.1$. Even though the V_{rad} in the annulus is close to zero, three positive areas of V_{rad} appear at high Φ . On the one hand, the greater sealing flow induces more egress from the cavity, on the other hand, the sealing flow egress is dominated by the stagnation of the blades.

FIGURE 10: THE RADIAL VELOCITY DISTRIBUTION AT THE CUTTING PLANE FOR THE RADIAL RIM SEAL

The radial velocity distribution of the radial rim seal is presented in **Fig. 10**. At $\Phi=0.001$, an obvious pair of the positive and negative V_{rad} is shown in the Profile3, indicating the larger total pressure near the hub induces the nonuniformity inside the rim. It is noticed is that a prominent area of the negative V_{rad} remains even though the Φ reaches 0.04, in comparison with almost no negative V_{rad} exists for the other profiles. This negative area indicates that the hot gas ingestion may be worse with a high total pressure near the hub.

4. CONCLUSION

In the presented work, a systematical computation was performed by the cases with four inlet total pressure profiles, two rim seal configurations and four sealing flowrates for each configuration. The conclusions are below:

The vane exit pressure difference, ΔC_p , is enhanced by the Profile3, of which the total pressure is the largest among the profiles studied. Even though the ΔC_p of the Profile3 reduces rapidly, it still reminds a scientific arrangement of measurement points to capture the reasonable flow characteristics.

The analysis of the V_{cir} and V_{rad} indicates that the radial velocity gradient may cause greater nonuniformity inside of the rim seal. And more hot gas ingestion occurs when meeting high total pressure near the hub.

Due to the limitations of the numerical method and computing resources, the research on the effect of the non-uniform inlet pressure on the hot ingestion still has many shortcomings. Advanced numerical simulation and experimental measurements need to be used for deeper insights and understandings for this topic.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the support of National Science and Technology Major Project (J2019-III-0007-0050) and (J2019-II-0008-0028)

REFERENCES

- [1] Scobie J.A., Sangan C.M., Michael Owen J., et al., Review of ingress in gas turbines[J]. *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, 2016, 138 (12).
- [2] Barringer M.D., Thole K.A., Polanka M.D., Experimental evaluation of an inlet profile generator for high-pressure turbine tests[J]. *Journal of Turbomachinery*, 2006, 129 (2): 382-393.
- [3] Barringer M.D., Thole K.A., Polanka M.D., An experimental study of combustor exit profile shapes on endwall heat transfer in high pressure turbine vanes[J]. *Journal of Turbomachinery*, 2009, 131 (2).
- [4] Wang Z., Wang D., Liu Z., et al., Numerical analysis on effects of inlet pressure and temperature non-uniformities on aero-thermal performance of a hp turbine[J]. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 2017, 104 83-97.
- [5] Simonassi L., Zenz M., Bruckner P., et al., Experimental study on the effect of clocking on the propagation of inflow pressure distortions in a low pressure turbine stage[R], in: *Proceedings of the ASME Turbo Expo 2020: Turbomachinery Technical Conference and Exposition*, 2020, Paper.
- [6] Wang Y., Zhang W., Li R., et al., Study on effects of inlet nonuniformities on aerothermal performance of NGV pressure side with different film cooling designs[J]. *Numerical Heat Transfer, Part A: Applications*, 2025, 86 (18): 6364-6385.
- [7] Li R., Wang L., Wang Z., et al., Uncertainty quantification for aerothermal characteristics of hp turbine vanes under combined hot-streak and turbulence intensity effects[J]. *Aerospace Research Communications*, 2025, Volume 3 - 2025.
- [8] Patinios M., Scobie J.A., Sangan C.M., et al., Measurements and modeling of ingress in a new 1.5-stage turbine research facility[J]. *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, 2017, 139 (1).
- [9] Scobie J.A., Hualca F.P., Patinios M., et al., Re-ingestion of upstream egress in a 1.5-stage gas turbine rig[J]. *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, 2018, 140 (7).
- [10] Scobie J.A., Hualca F.P., Sangan C.M., et al., Egress interaction through turbine rim seals[J]. *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, 2018, 140 (7).
- [11] Dawson M.G., Otter J.J., Atkins N.R., The effect of circumferential lengthscale on hot gas ingestion[R], in: *Proceedings of the ASME Turbo Expo 2022: Turbomachinery Technical Conference and Exposition*, 2022, Paper.
- [12] Graikos D., Tang H., Sangan C.M., et al., A new interpretation of hot gas ingress through turbine rim seals influenced by mainstream annulus swirl[J]. *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, 2022, 144 (11).
- [13] Savov S.S., Atkins N.R., A rim seal ingress model based on turbulent transport[R], in: *Proceedings of the Turbo Expo: Power for Land, Sea, and Air*, 2017, Paper V05BT15A009.
- [14] Monge-Concepción I., Siroka S., Berdanier R.A., et al., Influence of vane trailing edge flow on the formation of cavity cells and rim sealing[J]. *Journal of Turbomachinery*, 2022, 144 (6).
- [15] Mesny A.W., Pountney O.J., Scobie J.A., et al., Purge-mainstream interactions in a turbine stage with rotor endwall contouring[J]. *Journal of Turbomachinery*, 2024, 146 (9).
- [16] Barsi D., Biassoni D., Lengani D., et al., Sealing flow rate effects on unsteady loss production in a low pressure turbine stage[R], in: *Proceedings of the ASME Turbo Expo 2024: Turbomachinery Technical Conference and Exposition*, 2024, Paper.
- [17] Gao F., Chew J.W., Beard P.F., et al., Large-eddy simulation of unsteady turbine rim sealing flows[J]. *International Journal of Heat and Fluid Flow*, 2018, 70 160-170.
- [18] Gao F., Poujol N., Chew J.W., et al., Advanced numerical simulation of turbine rim seal flows and consideration for RANS turbulence modelling[R], in: *Proceedings of the Turbo Expo: Power for Land, Sea, and Air*, 2018, Paper V05BT15A005.
- [19] De Cosmo G., Scobie J.A., Lock G.D., et al., Fluid dynamics of turbine rim seal structures: A physical interpretation using URANS[J]. *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, 2022, 145 (3).
- [20] Xue Q., Li X., Ren J., Numerical investigations of flow structures in radial rim seal and a modification of the orifice model[R], in: *Proceedings of the ASME Turbo Expo 2022: Turbomachinery Technical Conference and Exposition*, 2022, Paper.
- [21] Xie L., Du Q., Liu G., et al., Turbine cavity mainstream ingestion assessing method based on penetration depth analysis[J]. *Journal of Turbomachinery*, 2024, 146 (8).
- [22] Burden S., Chew J.W., Gao F., et al., Effect of rim seal geometry on rotationally-driven ingestion[J]. *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, 2024, 1-12.
- [23] Cong Q., Lei L., Zhang K., et al., Effect of inflow swirl on the sealing effectiveness of turbine rim seal[R], in: *Proceedings of the ASME Turbo Expo 2023: Turbomachinery Technical Conference and Exposition*, 2023, Paper.